

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Students about Remote Work

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ABSTRACT

Remote work is one of the essential experiences that some people want to experience in the twentieth century. It is one of the results of the modern technological revolution. This study aimed to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) about remote work and to determine if they possess sufficient positive opinions and attributes that would help them thrive in the remote working environment in Türkiye, 2022. A cross-sectional survey was conducted between April and May 2022 using a self-developed structured questionnaire distributed online among students between Ondokuz Mayıs University students. Data were analyzed using a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) program version 25. The descriptive analysis includes tables and percentages to explain the data's main feature. The results showed that students have a high attitude and knowledge, Moderate level of practice toward remote work in Türkiye. The study also showed that students have a (moderate) level to practice remote work. The results also showed no statistically significant differences in answers of the study sample about students' knowledge, practice, and attitude about remote work due to the social demographic data variables. And there are no statistically significant differences in answers of the study sample about the Knowledge or practice of students about remote work due to the (Number of family members, Employment sector) variables. And The results also showed differences in the answers of the study sample about the attitude of students about remote work due to the (Number of family members, Employment sector) variables. Every remote worker should educate the community and students about the importance of remote work. Besides, there is a need for more studies to comprehensively investigate the various reasons that affect the lack of acceptance of remote work among some students and how they can be addressed.

1.INTRODUCTION

Research on the employment options of some university students during their studies is not a new thing in Türkiye or in other countries, but investigating the factors related to the remote work in the recent period has become popular among researchers and also became one of the most desired jobs for students, due to Covid 19 (Dundes and Marx, 2006). Remote student work may lead to the acquisition of graduates' job skills and their diversity, and the professionalization of higher education and the possibility of graduate employment (Pfeiffer, 2013). The economic crisis that Türkiye is going through has created an urgent need for students to work remotely. Therefore, this study aimed to determine students' knowledge, attitudes, and practice about remote work and if there is a significant relationship between students' socio demographic characteristics and working remotely or not.

1.1 Remote Work

The Weidig-O'Neil (2020) defined it as a way to work using information and communication technology so that the work is performed in isolation from the job place. Some studies indicate that there are about 50 definitions of remote work. There are several advantages to working remotely, such as providing a reduction in the space used by the company and the cost of office equipment, increasing productivity, less absenteeism, flexibility in working relationships, raising the level of quality of work, lowering the cost of rent, providing a better balance between work, life and time, reducing travel costs, increasing self-confidence, providing more job opportunities for women and the disabled. On the other hand, there are several disadvantages to working remotely, and such reasons are including the lack of direct control and supervision of employees, the high costs of preparing the house and preparing it to be ready for remote work, employee isolation, lack of teamwork, and lack of incentives (Pfeiffer, 2013; Weidig-O'Neil, 2020).

There are several factors for the success of remote work. Organizational confidence, organizational culture, knowledge about work, and previous experiences are the common factors affecting the overall performance of employees (Simosi, 2012). Despite the high demand of the remote work in recent years, there are many challenges involved such as some misconceptions among employees and managers, as not all employees or managers will accept the concept of remote work. The costs of providing the sufficient infrastructure for remote work is considered high expenses for many organizations. The manager who works in technology-

producing companies must have an open mind and a strategic, creative, and conscious personality. Implementing the remote work program successfully requires good infrastructure.

1.2 Remote Work in Türkiye

With the pandemic, Turkish companies have suddenly switched to the remote work system. It has been observed that remote work can be suitable for many sectors / industries. It is understood that telecommuting is particularly ideal for areas of work that perform office work, such as consulting, finance, marketing, computer and software technologies, human resources, and accounting.

Therefore, as envisioned, there is no doubt that remote work will bring about a transformation in the structure and way of doing business for companies in Türkiye. An interesting finding in a paper by Serinikli, N. (2021) it confirmed that the majority of companies, 72.9%, answered "yes" to the question "Should working from home be practiced more in your company after the Coronavirus epidemic?" Therefore, the remote work plan will be established in more companies in the coming period, and it will be Experts are needed in this regard. A study involving participants from 10 different cities revealed that as a result of interviews, two-thirds of those who work remotely are not in touch with their team, and more than one-third have never met face-to-face with their team (Adigüzel, 2020).

According to TURKSTAT, in 2016, 2.6% (610,771 people) of all private- sector employees worked at home; 89% of those working at home were women. In addition to the female-dominated structure of working at home in Türkiye, 87% of all workers worked informally. While it is seen that working at home has an informal and female-dominated nature, only 13% of those who work at home formally are women. Also, for 2019 data, 68.6% of those working at home are over 40. Compared to the overall age distribution in the labour market, this is a reasonably high average. 16% of those working at home are under the age of 35. As well for 2020 data, 49.6% of those working at home are primary school graduates, while 13.8% have never received any education. These ratios, which make up 63.4% of all home workers, show that the education level of home workers is low. Those with a university or higher education diploma, which makes up 9.3% of all home workers, constitute the highly educated part of homeworkers. According to 2017 data, the distribution of works performed at home by sector is as follows: domestic work (29%), textile manufacturing (22%), services related to buildings and landscaping activities (17%), and clothing production (10%) (Camp, Young, and Bushardt, 2022).

There are some main policy options to support workers and employers in remote work that is done in Türkiye: Providing up-to-date, reliable, and accessible information, Providing financial and administrative support and other assistance, and Easy some bureaucratic procedures, such as those on health and safety reviews of the home office environment, to allow remote working implementation, provided each employee conducts a self-assessment of their workplace, Providing flexibility and relaxing existing regulations as appropriate for example, the employer's obligation to provide ergonomic seating or sign a telework contract before the start of the teleworking period, to support remote workers. In the future, both private and public sector employers in Türkiye may consider employing more of their workforce remotely in the aftermath of the pandemic (Naktiyok and İşcan, 2003).

1.3 University Students Work

With the pandemic, Türkiye's companies have suddenly switched to the remote work system. It has been observed that remote work can be suitable for many jobs. It is understood that telecommuting is particularly ideal for areas of work that perform office work, such as consulting, finance, marketing, computer and software technologies, human resources, and accounting. It is not always easy for a young student to find a student job that matches his academic path or professional project, so if he finds such a job, he tries to take advantage of it to obtain practical experience. Many people accept a job that is not necessarily related to their studies to gain new experiences (Hovdhaugen, 2015).

Many students seek to work to develop their network. Getting a job for a student in addition to studying allows the student to meet many people! Indeed, it is an excellent opportunity to build his network. At work, students will have the chance to interact with other employers and meet new colleagues, service providers, and clients. As a result, in the future, the student may get priority access to vacancies from the company where the student worked previously. The student can also use this same network to connect with a potential employer. Finally, this network will also help the student get good recommendations. Finally, some applications work for reasons related to the presentation. You can, for example, carry out medium and long-term projects where the student's job is considered a glimpse into his future in the world of work. Thus, it will allow them to know their qualities and disadvantages (Lundberg, 2004).

In short, we can say that there are advantages and benefits to working while studying, including gaining work experience in the early stage, learning time management, earning

financial income, acquiring human references, and increasing self-knowledge. The student may also face some problems due to remote work, such as limited time, stress, fatigue, sleep, and social distancing (Akgül, 2016). There are many job opportunities for students to work remotely like being an online copywriter, a teacher for a foreign language online, online translator, online life coacher, videos editor, photos seller, blogger, etc. There are a lot of Turkish online platforms that students can work on such as : Armut, Bionluk, Sahibinden, Sadeceon, Sanal işçi, Proje kurdu, Webly (Göktepe, 2020).

2. METHODOLOGY

Previous studies indicate that this is a well-studied topic and while the importance and harms of remote work are well documented, the association of remote work with university students' knowledge, practices, and attitudes (aged 18- 25) is poorly understood. This study seeks to explain and examine the knowledge, attitude, and practice of Ondokuz Mayıs University students towards remote work. The study also aims to reveal the impact of social demographic information on remote work according to many variables such as gender, age, number of family members, etc.

Academic and randomized studies on linking university students to remote work are insufficient. Therefore, it isn't easy to fully understand the relationship between them. Consequently, it is believed that the research is essential in understanding the extent of knowledge, attitude and practice of students working remotely. On the other hand, the research findings are believed to be important in a better understanding of the determinants of remote work in university students and in guiding specific and targeted intervention strategies to improve these outcomes for this population. The study will also contribute to the community in providing suggestions for providing programs affiliated with Turkish universities that support students' work remotely by allocating certain hours calculated academically in which the work is applied remotely.

2.1 Limitations

The research was conducted at a single University in Türkiye. The sample used for this research were students registered during the period 28 April 2022 to 28 May 2022 at Ondokuz Mayıs University. The research assumes that the sample set was taken from the university through which the research was done in the community. In addition, the sample group participated objectively and thoughtfully in the survey. On the other hand, the researcher was neutral to the research group, and the survey responses were collected anonymously. The

research included only students who had no problem with communication (there were no psychological illnesses, they could speak English or Turkish and included only those who volunteered to participate in the research and were limited to students aged 18-25 years.

2.2 Sample Size

The sample size was determined as (214) based on a 95% confidence interval and 50% response selected by the simple random method, where questionnaires were distributed and (124) a questionnaire was retrieved with a percentage of (100%), All participants who meet the sampling criteria and agree to participate in the study are adults between 18-25 years old. The study sample included only bachelor's and master's students of both genders, male and female.

2.3 Data Collection Method and Materials

As a data collection tool, the Questionnaire containing two parts was prepared on Google Forms and then distributed to the participants. Online consent was obtained from all participants as they voluntarily participated in the research. The first part was related to the socio demographic information; eight questions start with age, gender, marital status, educational status, occupational status, economic status, number of members in the family, employment sector and presence of chronic diseases.

After answering the socio demographic questions, the participants answered the questions in the second part that related to their knowledge, attitude and practice about remote work. The Questionnaire was based on an shrm quiz, Queendom test, Harvard Business review questions and jotform. There are 21 questions, eight questions in the knowledge part of the scale, six in the practice part, and seven in the attitude part.

The data was collected online by sending the questionnaire via WhatsApp to the students. This research period lasted for three weeks when 124 volunteers responded. Each volunteer in the study was asked to complete a short questionnaire to assess their knowledge, practices and attitudes towards remote work.

The items of the scale of attitude were built according to a five-point scale and the weights were given to the items as follows: (Very Much: five degrees, Much: four degrees, middle: three degrees, little: two degrees, very little: one degree). This pentagonal scale has been applied to all paragraphs. In order to identify the estimates of the sample members and to determine the degree of (students practice about remote work), according to the value of the arithmetic mean, the range was calculated ($5-1 = 4$), then it was divided into (5) To get the correct cell length ($4/5 = 0.80$), then this value was added to the lowest value in the resolution (or the beginning

of the resolution which is the correct one) in order to determine the upper limit of this cell. For knowledge and Practice, if the answer is yes, there is one point; if it is no, zero.

2.4 Data Analysis

The obtained data were standardised appropriately and transferred to the SPSS 25.0 statistical program. In this context, firstly, statistical information (Frequency, Percentage) about the demographic characteristics of the participants is given. Then, explanatory factor analysis was performed to determine the factor structures related to the scales. After selecting the scale's factor structure, the factors obtained with the demographic groups were compared. For this, a sample t-test was applied since the groups showed normal distribution in group comparisons. One Way ANOVA tests were used in comparisons of more than two groups. For the reliability of the scale, the Cronbach Alpha value was examined.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Socio-Demographical Characteristics of the Participants

According to the Table No. 1, it is clear that concerning the distribution of students by work, a small number were over 22 years old and less than 19 years old (20.9%). The sample consisted of 80 males (64.5%) and 44 females (35.5%), and this may be due to social conditions. The sample consisted of 2 married (1.6%) and 122 single (98.4%). The sample consisted of 3 master's degrees (2.4%) and 121 bachelor's degrees (97.6%) students. The sample consisted of 26 students from low-income families (21%), 81 students from middle-income families (65.3%), and 17 students from high-income families (13.7%). The sample consisted of 4 students (3.2%) who had siblings, 118 students (95.2%) whose family members consisted of 4-7 members, and 2 students (1.6%) whose family members consisted of more than 8 members. As for the employment sector, most of the students, numbering 77 (62.1%), were not working, and then remote work came as a choice for students (18.5%), and in the last place was government work. Most students did not have chronic diseases (96.8%).

Variable	Variable Levels	Frequency (N)	Percentage %
Age	18	13	10.5
	19	21	16.9
	20	14	11.3
	21	13	10.5
	22	50	40.3
	23	7	5.6
	24	3	2.4
	25	3	2.4
Total		124	100.0
Gender	Male	80	64.5
	Female	44	35.5
Total		124	100.0
Marital status	Married	2	1.6
	Single	122	98.4
Total		124	100.0
Education level	Bachelor	121	97.6
	Master's	3	2.4
	PhD	---	---
Total		124	100.0
Economic status	High	26	21.0
	Mid	81	65.3

Table 1: Distribution of Socio-Demographical Characteristics of the Participants

3.2 Students' knowledge level toward remote work

We note from the previous table and through the data in the table that level of students' knowledge of remote work were at a (high) degree, where the arithmetic mean was (1.91) with a standard deviation (0.103). Referring to the table (2) we find that students have knowledge of remote work by (91.1%) in the total degree, and this percentage is high, so students have a high level of knowledge from work remotely. The results in the previous table indicate that all items of the students' knowledge scale have a high degree, and this indicates the students' prior knowledge about remote work.

No	Scale Questions	Answer		Yes Percentage (%)	Arithmetic Average (AV)	Standard Deviation (Std)	Degree
		Yes	No				
1	Does remote work mean “is an employment arrangement in which employees do not commute to a central place of work, such as an office building, warehouse, or retail store and it is facilitated by technology.”?	115	9	92.7%	1.93	0.260	High
2	Does remote work have certain rules in every country?	99	25	79.8%	1.80	0.403	High
3	Are there a number of companies that do remote work?	124	0	100%	2	0.00	High
4	Are each of these popular programs a model for remote working? Zoom, Cisco Webex, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, Slack, and WhatsApp?	124	0	100%	2	0.000	High
5	Did the Corona period have a positive impact on remote work, as the number of remote workers increased?	113	11	91.1%	1.91	0.285	High
6	Does remote work in general result in reduced energy use due to less time spent on energy-intensive personal transportation?	108	16	87.1%	1.87	0.337	High
7	Do global companies such as Google and Netflix follow the policy of remote work with their employees?	112	12	90.3%	1.90	0.297	High

Table 2: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations students' knowledge of remote work

The results in the table 3 indicate that the most important medium that students use to obtain information about remote work is social networking sites or what it called social media, with a percentage of (83.9%). It can be said that university students are accustomed to electronic research and information acquisition through social media, so this percentage represents the university youth group in a logical way to reality.

Method(intermediary)		Frequency	Percent t
Method	social media	104	83.9
	Books	6	4.8
	Magazines	1	.8
	Broadcast media	5	4.0
	Television	6	4.8
	Audio and casts	2	1.6
	Total	124	100.0

Table 3: Sources of knowledge about remote work

3.3 Students' knowledge level toward remote work

The previous table and through the data in the table that the attitude of students working remotely were at a (high) degree, where the arithmetic mean was (3.67) with a standard deviation (0.474). The results also indicated that the level of confidence in working remotely and that it brings an appropriate material income, was at a high degree where the arithmetic mean was (4.08) with a standard deviation (0.959). The results showed that the student's level of belief that remote workers are greater than necessary was at a high degree where the arithmetic mean was (3.94) with a standard deviation (0.922). And the level of benefit of remote work in the future in achieving its goals was at a high degree, where the arithmetic mean was (4.19) with a standard deviation (0.925). The results showed that the student's level of belief that there are shortcomings and difficulties in how to work remotely was at a middle degree, where the arithmetic mean was (3.24) with a standard deviation (1.205). The results indicated that the student's level of belief that remote work will be a safer and more reliable future than

it is today, was at a high degree where the arithmetic mean was (3.94) with a standard deviation (1.057). The results indicated that the student's level of belief that there is a fair distribution of remote work in Türkiye was at a high degree where the arithmetic mean was (3.41) with a standard deviation (1.189). The student's level of worrying about working remotely was at a middle degree where the arithmetic mean was (2.91) with a standard deviation (1.196).

NO.	Scale Questions	Answer					Arithmetic average (AV)	Standard Deviation (Std)	Degree
		very little	little	Middle	much	Too much			
1	How much you are confident in working remotely and that it brings a suitable financial income	3	5	19	49	48	4.08	1.192	High
2	How much do you think that remote workers are too big?	0	11	23	52	38	3.94	0.959	High
3	How much do you think that remote work has benefit in the future in achieving its goals	0	7	22	35	60	4.19	0.922	High
4	How much do you think that there are shortcomings and difficulties in how to work remotely in your country	12	22	34	36	20	3.24	0.925	middle
5	How much do you think that remote work will be a safer and more reliable future than today	3	11	22	43	45	3.94	1.205	High
6	How much do you think that there is a fair distribution of remote work in Türkiye	8	19	40	28	29	3.41	1.057	High
7	In general, how much do you think that you are worried about working remotely.	17	30	37	27	13	2.91	1.189	middle
The attitude of students working remotely		43	105	197	270	253	3.67	0.474	High

Table 4: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations the attitude of students working remotely

3.4 Students' knowledge level toward remote work

The results in Table 5 indicate that the level of students was moderate, as the answer rate is yes on the total paragraphs of the field was (58.6%), my account average (1.59), and a standard deviation (0.236). The results in the table indicated that students who work remotely have great confidence in remote work and have good economic income. The paragraph came in a high degree with an arithmetic mean (1.71) and a standard deviation (0.456), while paragraph No. (5) stated that the student had fears in the future regarding remote work at a high degree, with an arithmetic mean (1.70) and a standard deviation (0.459), and paragraph No. (6), which provided for the student's support for colleagues who are trying to work remotely, came to a high degree, with an arithmetic mean (1.80) and a standard deviation (0.403).

No.	Scale	Answer				Arithmetic average (AV)	Standard Deviation (Std)
		Yes	%	No	%		
1	I have worked or am now working in remote work	50	40.3	74	59.7	1.40	0.493
2	One of my colleagues has worked or is working remotely	55	44.4	69	55.6	1.44	0.499
3	I have great confidence in working remotely and that it has a good economic income	88	71	36	29	1.71	0.456
4	I prefer remote work to real work	57	46	67	54	1.46	0.500
5	I have no future concerns about remote work	87	70.2	37	29.8	1.70	0.459
6	I try to support all of my colleagues who try to work remotely	99	79.8	25	20.2	1.80	0.403
The level of students practices remote work		436	58.6	308	41.4	1.59	0.236

Table 5: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations students' the level of students practices remote work

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study showed that the level of students' knowledge of remote work was a (high) level. The most important source that students use to obtain information about remote work was social media sites, with a percentage of (83.9%). The previous result indicates that students have a high percentage of knowledge about remote work and its importance due to the great interest that remote work has occupied in the past two years, especially after the emergence of covid-19. Also, social media sites settled the most popular source to get information from it due to the ease of access to those sites and the sharing of knowledge and files through them and because of the development of technology and the emergence of many of those sites that do not need much experience to know how to use it.

Companies are competing among them in developing communication applications to become more accessible and easier for people when using them, all of this has made them a fertile source for students to draw information from. The results showed that students have a high attitude toward remote work in Türkiye. The results indicate that there is a positive attitude for students about remote work in Türkiye due to the great importance of remote work in improving the student's income, especially in light of the current situation of high prices not only in Türkiye but in the whole world, on the other hand, we can attribute the positive attitude of students about remote work, which in terms of providing the worker with flexible working hours to that employee does not adhere to specific working hours at which led students going to work remotely.

The study also demonstrated that students have a (moderate) level to practice remote work. The previous result indicates that the practice of students working remotely at a medium degree, due to several factors, including Remote work, is flexible and does not require much effort; on the one hand, its wages are limited and low, and the orientation of companies and the market towards remote work is considered new, as it has spread vigorously only over the past two years as a result of the government's strict measures to reduce the covid-19 pandemic. Remote work is a double-edged sword as it is possible for the employee to be scammed and defrauded, especially if he is new and has no experience in this field, as there are many fake advertisements for remote work and its primary goal is to pinch and defraud people, all of these led to a weak desire among students to take the risk in working remotely.

The results showed no statistically significant differences in answers of the study sample about Knowledge, practice, and attitude of students about remote work due to (gender, Marital status, Education level, Economic status, Age, and chronic disease) variables. In addition, there are no statistically significant differences in answers of the study sample about the Knowledge

or practice of students about remote work due to the (Number of family members, Employment sector) variables. And The results also showed differences in the answers of the study sample about the attitude of students about remote work due to the (Number of family members, Employment sector) variables.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, it is recommended that students learn 1. to manage their time; for instance, to avoid jobs that finish late in the evening as this will pose a risk of fatigue the next day in class. 2. It is recommended for students who work part-time to themselves between classes and work, as their schedule is likely to be very busy. However, they should remember to take a break from time to time. 3. It is advised to avoid work contracts that require a lot of time. 4. Students who work remotely, regardless of their contract type, are advised to maintain good relations with those at work. 5. It is advised to make a good impression and does their best for the duration of the contract. 6. Students are advised to develop their teleworking skills.

This study was conducted only at a one University in Türkiye. The study could be extended to more Universities or/at national level. Also, it would be interesting to investigate the similar studies in different contexts.

RESOURCES

- Adigüzel, M. (2020). Covid-19 pandemisinin Türkiye ekonomisine etkilerinin makroekonomik analizi. *İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 19(37), 191-221.
- Akgül, Y. (2016, June). Quality evaluation of E-government websites of Turkey. In 2016 11th Iberian conference on information systems and technologies (CISTI) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- Camp, K. M., Young, M., & Bushardt, S. C. (2022). A millennial manager skills model for the new remote work environment. *Management Research Review*.
- Dundes, L., & Marx, J. (2006). Balancing work and academics in college: Why do students working 10 to 19 hours per week excel?. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 8(1), 107-120.
- Göktepe, E. A. (2020). A Phenomenological Research to Determine Individuals' Perception of Distance (Work From Home) Model in Pandemic Period; Public University Example. *Journal of Current Researches on Business and Economics*, 10(1), 29-42.
- Hovdhaugen, E. (2015). Working while studying: The impact of term-time employment on dropout rates. *Journal of Education and Work*, 28(6), 631-651.
- Lundberg, C. A. (2004). Working and learning: The role of involvement for employed students. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 41(2), 400-414.
- Naktiyok, A., & İşcan, Ö. F. (2003). İşgörenlerin evden çalışmaya ilişkin tutumları: Bireysel özellikler ve iş sürükleyicileri açısından bir uygulama. *Akdeniz İİBF Dergisi*, 3(6), 53-72.
- Pfeiffer, S. I. (2013). Lessons learned from working with high-ability students. *Gifted Education International*, 29(1), 86-97.
- Simosi, M. (2012). The moderating role of self - efficacy in the organizational culture-training transfer relationship. *International journal of training and development*, 16(2), 92-106.
- Weidig-O'Neil, M. L. (2020). IS Mechanisms and Organizational Performance Mediated Through IS Management (Doctoral dissertation, Trident University International).